

A new, high-yielding mutant aromatic rice variety, Khushboo 95

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Rice is grown on 2.5 million ha in Pakistan. The average yield is 2.1 t ha⁻¹. During the 1960s, with the introduction of semidwarf varieties IR6 and IR8, yields doubled and most of the traditional fine-grained aromatic varieties went out of cultivation. However, Basmati 370, a traditional scented variety, survived to a certain extent. Another local aromatic variety, Jajai 77, is very popular with consumers in the province of Sindh. This variety is tall, has weak stems, and is susceptible to lodging. The most logical approach to remove these defects without impairing grain quality is to reduce plant height through induced mutation, a technique that proved successful in improving various agronomic traits in rice (Mustafa et al 1997, Singh et al 1997, Wen et al 1996, Baloch et al 2001).

Pure and viable uniform seeds of Jajai 77 were irradiated with 200 Gy of gamma rays at the International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria, in 1981 and the M₁ generation was grown at NIA. Plants were selected on the basis of synchronous early flowering, increased tillering, and reduced plant height in the M₂, M₃, and M₄ generations during 1982, 1983, and 1984, respectively. The high-yielding, short-culm mutant line Jajai 77-30 with aromatic characteristics was eventually selected in 1984. The mutant

has the following characteristics: reduced plant height, highly productive tillers, early maturity, increased panicle length, more grains per panicle, good grain quality, and distinct aroma.

Station varietal trials were conducted at two locations—Tando jam and Rice Research Institute, in Dokri, Sindh Province. The results were pooled over locations and years and data for grain yield were analyzed. The pooled analysis indicated significant ($P \leq 0.05$) differences in grain yield when averaged over locations and years. The mutant Jajai 77-30 consistently outyielded (5.3 t ha⁻¹) all other entries. Its grain yield was 74%, 77%, and 81% higher than that of commercial variety Jajai 77, Basmati 370, and Lateefy, respectively.

Jajai 77-30, along with other promising genotypes, was evaluated in zonal trials over 10 locations in Sindh from 1988 to 1990.

This mutant outyielded all other entries in these trials. In coordinated national uniform rice yield trials conducted by the Pakistan Agricultural Research Council (PARC), Islamabad, from 1989 to 1991, Jajai 77-30 was the top and second-best yielder over various locations in Pakistan (3.7–4.2 t ha⁻¹) and in Sindh (3,724–4,483 kg ha⁻¹), respectively.

Jajai 77-30, named Khushboo 95, was approved for general cultivation in the province by the Sindh Seed Council in 1996. Now a prominent rice variety, it is grown on large areas in Dadu, Sanghar, and Jacobabad districts of Sindh and in Hafizabad District of Punjab. Yields ranged from 3.7 to 5.0 t ha⁻¹, which were substantially higher than those of well-adapted local aromatic varieties. The grain chalkiness of Khushboo 95 was much lower than that of the parent (see table).

Agronomic characteristics of mutant variety Jajai 77-30 (Khushboo 95) and its parent Jajai 77.

Characteristic	Jajai 77-30 (Khushboo 95)	Jajai 77	Increase over parent (%)
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.4	2.1	52
Productive tillers plant ⁻¹ (no.)	14.45	10.68	26
Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	148	88	41
Length/breadth	3.24	3.07	5
Head rice (%)	44.0	41.5	6
Chalkiness (%)	25.0	68.83	64 (decrease)
Amylose content (%)	20.80	19.81	5
Plant height (cm)	130	160	19 (decrease)
Proportionate elongation	1.55	1.50	3